

**Literature Review Bibliography:
Energy Security in the Era of Hybrid Warfare**

Peter Burgherr

Technology Assessment Group

Laboratory for Energy Systems Analysis

Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI)

Villigen PSI, Switzerland

Corresponding author: peter.burgherr@psi.ch

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